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**Comparison of model results from simulations
with grid resolution 4 and 20 km**

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Abstract

The second largest gas field in Norway, Ormen Lange, is located at Storegga 140 km west of Kristiansund. Ormen Lange lies in the continental shelf slope where several slides have created a rough bottom topography. The seabed above the reservoir is located at 800 to 1100 m depth.

Two three-dimensional, time split, σ -coordinate models are set up. Their grid resolutions are 20 and 4 km. In order to capture some of the unresolved physics in the 20 km model, the two models will be run with corresponding bottom topography and initial conditions. As external force, an idealised travelling low pressure will be used.

The model results show that the 20 km model gives higher maximum speed and stronger oscillations for the deeper locations than the 4 km model. The 4 km model gives stronger oscillations at shallow parts, but the damping is stronger in this model, so this is only the case for a short time after the storm has passed.

Initially the 20 km model shows a northern current at the shallow locations. The initial currents at the deeper locations are very small. The 4 km model has initially a fairly strong southern current for the deeper locations. In the shallow area the current is directed more toward the north.

1 Introduction

Ormen Lange is the second largest gas field in Norway and is located in the Storegga region approximately 130 km offshore of mid-Norway. Ormen Lange lies in the core of where several submarine slides have taken place. This means the seabed is covered with high escarpments and local sea mounts. The seabed depth above the reservoir varies between 700 and 1100 m. This is the first deep water hydrocarbon project outside the Norwegian shelf.

Bottom topography, as at Ormen Lange, is known to produce physics at different length scales. A lot of this physics is not resolved by the numeric model, since the grid size is the limiting factor ($2\Delta x$) for resolving physics. For the simulations at Ormen Lange, that are focusing on the travelling low pressures and the thermohaline circulation, only the physics on the relatively large scale are resolved.

Two model runs are performed with the same bottom matrix, but with different grid resolution. One will have a grid resolution of 20 km. This will cover the Norwegian Sea basin. The other will cover the eastern part of the Norwegian Sea and have 4 km as the horizontal grid resolution. The same idealised low pressure will be passing through the two model domains. The effects of unresolved physics in the 20 km grid resolution model will then be studied in time series of speed, velocities, temperature and salinity. Figures of these time series are made at 5 different locations (Table 1) in the Ormen Lange area, see Figure 1 and Figure 2, at 10 and 50 m above the seabed.

Model	OL1	OL2	OL3	OL4	OL5
4 km	227.8	615.0	851.8	1191.0	826.2
20 km	257.0	499.0	835.9	1120.1	764.4

Table 1: Depths in meters at stations OL1 to OL5

(a) Domain 20 km grid resolution model.

(b) Domain 4 km grid resolution model.

Figure 1: Model area given in grid coordinates. The Ormen Lange area is outlined.

(a) The Ormen Lange area (20 km).

(b) The Ormen Lange area (4 km).

Figure 2: Ormen Lange with the locations OL1-OL5.

2 Model

This model study uses the numerical σ -coordinate ocean model of Berntsen (2000). The equations are the continuity equation for an incompressible fluid, the Reynold averaged hydrostatic momentum equations, conservation equations for temperature and salinity and the UNESCO-equation of state. The reader is referred to Berntsen (2000) for further details concerning the governing equations and numerical methods.

The 20 km horizontal grid resolution model covers the Norwegian Sea basin, Figure 1 a), and the 4 km horizontal grid resolution model covers the south eastern part of the Norwegian Sea basin, Figure 1 b). In the vertical 30 σ -layers are applied and these are distributed according to a formula given in Lynch et al. (1995). The formula distributes the layers symmetrically about the midpoint in the vertical with a gradually finer resolution towards the surface and the bottom.

Both models are run for 240 hours, with 30 2-D time steps per 3-D step. The internal 3-D time step in the 20 km model is 360 s, and in the 4 km model 120s. Initial values of water elevation, velocities, temperature and salinity from Eldevik et al. (2001) are used. These are interpolated from 20 km into the 4 km grid.

At the lateral open boundaries, a flow relaxation scheme (FRS) is implemented (Martinsen and Engedahl, 1987). The FRS-zones are 7 grid-cells wide. In the 20 km grid resolution model, flow to and from the Baltic is implemented after an algorithm due to Stigebrandt (1980). Fresh water runoff from rivers around the North Sea is included in the models. For experiments over longer periods, this forcing will strongly affect the coastal circulation, but in the present study this forcing has minor importance.

In addition to the initial values for water elevation (η), velocity (u and v), temperature (T) and salinity (S) four tidal constituents (M_2 , S_2 , K_1 , N_2), are used to specify the lateral boundary conditions.

Travelling low pressure systems are important driving mechanisms for the oceanic flow. Martinsen et al. (1979) constructed a model of a cyclone and studied barotropic effects of the moving cyclone. The atmospheric pressure disturbance is described by, following Martinsen et al. (1979),

$$p(x, y, t) = p_0(t)e^{\{-(x-x_0-u_0t)^2+(y-y_0-v_0t)^2\}/R^2} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where $p_0(t)$ is the pressure disturbance at the center of the cyclone, x_0 , y_0 the initial position of the center of the pressure disturbance, u_0 , v_0 are the x and y components of the propagation velocity and R defines the horizontal extent of the pressure disturbance. Wind velocity components u_g and v_g in x and y

Experiment		x_0	y_0
20 km	(RUN_R500)	-21.13	100.42
4 km		-235.65	372.08

Table 2: Starting positions of the idealised atmospheric low pressure in grid coordinates. In parentheses the corresponding simulations in Vikebø et al. (2001).

directions, respectively, are computed from the gradients in the atmospheric pressure.

$$u_g = -\frac{0.7}{f\rho_a} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \quad , \quad (2)$$

$$v_g = \frac{0.7}{f\rho_a} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \quad . \quad (3)$$

Above f is the Coriolis parameter and ρ_a the density of the air (1.3 kgm^{-3}).

From the wind velocity, wind stress is computed

$$\tau_x = \rho_a c_D (u_g^2 + v_g^2)^{1/2} u_g \quad , \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_y = \rho_a c_D (u_g^2 + v_g^2)^{1/2} v_g \quad , \quad (5)$$

where c_D is the drag coefficient. In our experiments c_D is chosen to be 3×10^{-3} (cf. Martinsen et al. 1979).

The strongest response on the currents at Ormen Lange occurs when the maximum wind speed is approximately along the shelf slope, Vikebø et al. (2001). This response can be achieved by choosing starting points for the travelling low pressure (x_0, y_0) , as in Table 2, and setting the propagation velocities $u_0 = 8.59 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and $v_0 = -4.81 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. This means that the low pressure in the 20 km and the 4 km model has corresponding paths.

The low pressures are started at the initial positions (x_0, y_0) . The first 24 hours $p_0(t) = 0$. The pressure disturbance $p_0(t)$ is then increased linearly over the next 12 hours to $p_0 = -60 \text{ hPa}$ and held constant for the remaining simulation period.

The radius of the low pressure is 500 km. The distance between the center and the point with maximum wind speed is 353.6 km ($R/\sqrt{2}$).

3 Model Results

At all locations, the 20 km grid resolution model produces higher maximum speed than the 4 km model, even if the initial speed in the 4 km model (OL3

and OL4) is higher (see Figure 3 and Figure 4). This may indicate that there is a flow of energy from the larger spatial scales to the smaller scales that is underestimated in the 20 km model. With higher horizontal resolution, the smaller scale processes are better resolved. The interactions between processes on larger and smaller scales are also better represented in the 4 km model. The noticeable differences in the time series show that processes on spatial scales less than 2×20 km, that are not represented in the 20 km grid, are important in studies of extreme near seabed velocities.

From the horizontal velocity figures (Figure 5 -8) the results from the 4 km model show an initial southern flow and a flow towards the coast for the deeper locations (OL3, OL4 and OL5) that are not found in the results from the 20 km model. Observations also show that the deeper Norwegian Sea Arctic Intermediate Water masses, that are found below the Atlantic Water masses, may flow towards the south. The model results from the 4 km model are thus in quantitative agreement with the observations. The 4 km model also responds with stronger oscillations in the shallow areas (OL1 and OL2) after the storm has passed than the 20 km model. These oscillations are damped more rapidly in the 4 km model results. The largest differences in maximum values between the two sets of results, are found in the velocities in the along slope direction.

At the more shallow locations, the amplitude of the vertical oscillations is much larger in the results from the 4 km model, see Figure 9 and 10. These strong vertical excursions also affect the temperature and salinity fields, see Figure 11 to 14. On the other hand, at the deeper locations, the vertical oscillations tend to be stronger in the results from the 20 km model, see Figure 9 and 10.

4 Discussion

The most notable differences between the results from the 20 km model and the results from the 4 km model are:

- the flow produced by the 4 km model is much more focused around the shelf edge.
- the maximum velocities are larger in the 20 km model
- the internal oscillations after the storm are more rapidly damped in the results from the 4 km model
- in contrast to the 20 km model, the 4 km model is able to reproduce the observed southward flow in the deeper water masses.

The explanation for these differences is that with the 20 km grid resolution there are important unresolved physical phenomena. With this coarse resolution, the viscosity become large. As a result of these two conditions the shelf edge flow will typically become too wide. With 4 km resolution the flow at the shelf edge, and along the shelf slope will be better represented. However, there may still be sub-grid scale effects of major importance to the flow in general, but also to the peak velocities, see description in Berntsen and Furnes (2002). To run models with higher resolution, that also cover the whole Ormen Lange area, is very expensive with todays computers. Therefore, it is important to develop methods for parametrisation of sub-grid scale studies.

It may also be noted that both sets of experiments reported on here, are performed with climatological fields of temperature and salinity. These fields are very smooth when compared to in-situ measurements. In reality, it is a thin pycnocline between the Atlantic Water masses and the Norwegian Sea water masses. Many of the events seen in observed time series, are related to oscillations of this interface. To realistically model such oscillations also requires high resolution, both horizontally and vertically.

Model studies with model areas covering the extended Ormen Lange will therefore not be able to properly represent all major length scales. They should therefore be supported by idealised studies with fine scale topography, realistic stratifications and grid resolutions that allow representation of the topography and the stratification.

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(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 3: Time series of speed OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Results from 20km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 4: Time series of speed OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Results from 20km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 5: Time series of velocity in x -direction OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Results from 20 km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 6: Time series of velocity in x -direction OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Results from 20 km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 7: Time series of velocity in y -direction OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Results from 20 km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 8: Time series of velocity in y -direction OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Results from 20 km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 9: Time series of velocity in z -direction OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Results from 20 km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 10: Time series of velocity in z -direction OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Results from 20 km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 11: Time series of salinity OL1-OL5, 10m above the sea bed. Results from 20km model (solid line) and from 4km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 12: Time series of salinity OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Results from 20km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 13: Time series of temperature OL1-OL5, 10m above the sea bed. Results from 20km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 14: Time series of temperature OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Results from 20km model (solid line) and from 4 km (dotted line).

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